

THERMALLY INDUCED DEFORMATIONS IN VISCOELASTIC COMPOSITE BEAMS UNDER PIEZOELECTRIC CONTROL OF PROBABILISTIC SURVIVAL TIMES

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ABSTRACT

Analytical and numerical formulations and simulations are carried out in order to conduct sensitivity studies of physical affecting parameters motion and amplitude control by viscoelastic piezoelectric and material damping of viscoelastic beams under thermal loadings. Numerical simulations in terms of critical parameters, such as relaxation functions of the structure and piezoelectric devices, are carried out to evaluate system responses, sensing and structural control.

Keywords: beams, creep, failure probabilities, material damping, piezo structural control, survivability, thermal stresses, viscoelasticity

INTRODUCTION

Composites are well known to creep, relax and delaminate with time, temperature and moisture dependent rates following well established viscoelastic constitutive relations [1 – 5]. Elastic piezoelectric analyses were established in [6 – 8], while piezo-viscoelastic theory was developed in [9]. Extensive experimental data describing piezo-viscoelastic responses are found in [10 – 14]. Viscoelastic material properties are extremely sensitive to temperature changes – a 20°C variation produces an order of magnitude change in relaxation times – resulting in highly non-homogeneous materials

In the present paper, stress and deformation analyses are formulated and evaluated for composite beams with temperature distributions across their faces that induce time dependent bending and shear deformations. These pilot problems are used as a vehicle for sensitivity studies of physical parameters affecting thermal and piezoelectric structural control to alleviate or possibly eliminate undesirable thermal stresses. Numerical simulations in terms of critical characteristics are carried out to evaluate system responses, sensing and structural control. Some other examples of elastic and viscoelastic piezoelectric control are given in [15 – 19].

Viscoelastic relaxation moduli and delamination stresses degrade with time [20], thus introducing the concept of structural life or survival time. The failure conditions are based on the concept of probabilistic invariant failure surfaces developed in [21]. There are, of course, instances where stress relaxation rates are greater than the independent degradation rates of delamination stresses. In such cases the structure has the possibility of very long viscoelastic lifetimes. However, more realistic and of greater expectations are the present results, where internal stresses increase in time resulting in larger failure probabilities and shorter finite survival times.

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ANALYSIS

Beam bending

Consider a prismatic beam as shown in Fig. 1 of length L and height $2h$ and width b with strips of piezo-viscoelastic devices on the upper and lower surfaces aligned in the longitudinal x_1 -direction. A Cartesian coordinate system $x = x_i$ with $i = 1, 2, 3$ is used as reference. The beam, piezo devices and bonding material are all considered as viscoelastic, but having distinct responses, i. e. relaxation moduli. A temperature distribution $T(x_2, t)$ is applied across the face of the beam in order to induce pure bending. The respective constitutive relations for the bending stresses σ_{11} , shear stresses σ_{12} and electric displacements D_i are given by

$$\begin{aligned}
 \sigma_{11}(x_1, x_2, t) = & \underbrace{SW(x_2) \int_{-\infty}^t \widehat{\phi}(\xi - \xi') \frac{\partial \widehat{\epsilon}_{11}(x_1, x_2, \xi')}{\partial \xi'} d\xi'}_{\text{bending strain}} \\
 & - \underbrace{SW(x_2) \int_{-\infty}^t \widehat{\phi}^{\mathbf{T}}(\xi^{\mathbf{T}} - \xi') \frac{\partial [\widehat{\alpha T}(x_2, \xi')]}{\partial \xi'} d\xi'}_{\text{thermal expansion strain}} - \underbrace{SW^{\mathbf{B}}(x_2) \int_{-\infty}^t \widehat{\phi}^{\mathbf{B}}(\xi^{\mathbf{B}} - \xi') \frac{\partial \widehat{\epsilon}_{11}(x_1, x_2, \xi')}{\partial \xi'} d\xi'}_{\text{bonding strain}} \\
 & - \underbrace{SW^{\mathbf{P}}(x_2) \int_{-\infty}^t \widehat{\phi}^{\mathbf{P}}(\xi^{\mathbf{P}} - \xi') \frac{\partial \widehat{\mathcal{E}}_1(x_1, x_2, \xi')}{\partial \xi'} d\xi'}_{\text{piezo strain}} \tag{1}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 D_1(x_1, x_2, t) = & SW^{\mathbf{D}}(x_2) \left[\underbrace{\int_{-\infty}^t \widehat{\phi}^{\mathbf{D}}(\xi^{\mathbf{D}} - \xi') \frac{\partial \widehat{\epsilon}_{11}(x_1, x_2, \xi')}{\partial \xi'} d\xi'}_{\text{bending strains}} \right. \\
 & \left. - \underbrace{\int_{-\infty}^t \widehat{\phi}^{\mathbf{DT}}(\xi^{\mathbf{DT}} - \xi') \frac{\partial [\widehat{\alpha T}(x_2, \xi')]}{\partial \xi'} d\xi'}_{\text{thermal expansions}} \right] + \underbrace{SW^{\mathbf{DP}}(x_2) \int_{-\infty}^t \widehat{\phi}^{\mathbf{DP}}(\xi^{\mathbf{DP}} - \xi') \frac{\partial \widehat{\mathcal{E}}_1(x_1, x_2, \xi')}{\partial \xi'} d\xi'}_{\text{piezo strains}} \tag{2}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\sigma_{12}(x_1, x_2, t) = \int_{-\infty}^t \widehat{\phi}^{\mathbf{S}}(\xi^{\mathbf{S}} - \xi') \frac{\partial \widehat{\epsilon}_{12}(x_1, x_2, \xi')}{\partial \xi'} d\xi' = \int_{x_2}^h \frac{\partial \sigma_{11}(x_1, \widetilde{x}_2, t)}{\partial x_1} d\widetilde{x}_2 \tag{3}$$

where the switches SW are

$$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} SW(x_2), SW^{\mathbf{D}}(x_2) \\ SW^{\mathbf{B}}(x_2) \\ SW^{\mathbf{P}}(x_2), SW^{\mathbf{DP}}(x_2) \end{array} \right\} = \left\{ \begin{array}{l} H(x_2) - H(x_2 - h) \\ H(x_2 - h) - H(x_2 - h - h_B) \\ H(x_2 - h - h_B) - H(x_2 - h - h_B - h_P) \end{array} \right\} \quad (4)$$

and the reduced times ξ are defined in terms of rheologically simple time–temperature shift functions a_T as

$$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} \xi(x_2, t) \\ \xi^{\mathbf{M}}(x_2, t) \end{array} \right\} = \int_{-\infty}^t \left\{ \begin{array}{l} a_T [T(x_2, t')] \\ a_T^{\mathbf{M}} [T(x_2, t')] \end{array} \right\} dt' \quad (5)$$

where \mathbf{M} represents anyone of the materials denoted by \mathbf{T} , \mathbf{B} , \mathbf{P} , \mathbf{D} , \mathbf{DT} , \mathbf{DP} and \mathbf{S} .

A relatively simple form of the shift factor is [22]

$$\log a_T = \frac{-C_1(M) (T - T_0)}{C_2(M) + T - T_0} \quad (6)$$

where the C_1 and C_2 are moisture dependent material property parameters. At the reference temperature T_0 , $a_T = 1$ and it follows that then $\xi = t$. If one wanted to apply the elastic–viscoelastic integral transform analogy, then the following approximations need to be introduced [2]

$$\begin{aligned} \xi(x_2, t) &\approx \xi^{\mathbf{T}}(x_2, t) \approx \xi^{\mathbf{B}}(x_2, t) \approx \xi^{\mathbf{P}}(x_2, t) \approx \\ \xi^{\mathbf{D}}(x_2, t) &\approx \xi^{\mathbf{DT}}(x_2, t) \approx \xi^{\mathbf{DP}}(x_2, t) \approx \xi^{\mathbf{S}}(x_2, t) \end{aligned} \quad (7)$$

in order to be able to evaluate the necessary Laplace or Fourier transforms throughout the beam, bonding material and the piezo devices.

The solution can be obtained by invoking the usual Bernoulli–Euler assumption that plane sections remain plane [23], such that

$$\epsilon_{11}(x_2, t) = k(t) x_2 \quad (8)$$

where the function $k(t)$ determined by the boundary conditions as

$$\int_{-h^*}^{h^*} \sigma(x_2, t) b dx_2 = N_T(t) \quad \text{and} \quad \int_{-h^*}^{h^*} \sigma(x_2, t) x_2 b dx_2 + 2 h \mathcal{N}^{\mathbf{P}}(t) = M_3(t) \quad (9)$$

with $h^* = h + h_B + h_P$. The forces $N_T(t)$ and moments $M_3(t)$ are determined by the temperature distribution $T(x_2, t)$ and equal and opposite piezo shear constraints $\mathcal{N}^{\mathbf{P}}(t)$ on the upper and lower faces of the beam. Substituting from Eqs. (1) yields

$$\int_{-\infty}^t \frac{dk(t')}{dt'} \underbrace{\int_{-h}^h \widehat{\phi}(x_2, \xi - \xi') x_2 dz_2 dt'}_{F_1(t,t')} - \underbrace{\int_{-\infty}^t \int_{-h}^h \widehat{\phi}^{\mathbf{T}}(x_2, \xi^{\mathbf{T}} - \xi') \frac{\partial [\widehat{\alpha T}(x_2, \xi')]}{\partial \xi'} dx_2 dt'}_{F_2(t)} = \frac{N_T(t)}{b} \quad (10)$$

$$\int_{-\infty}^t \frac{dk(t')}{dt'} \underbrace{\int_{-h}^h \widehat{\phi}(x_2, \xi - \xi') x_2^2 dz_2 dt'}_{F_3(t,t')} - \underbrace{\int_{-\infty}^t \int_{-h}^h \widehat{\phi}^{\mathbf{T}}(x_2, \xi^{\mathbf{T}} - \xi') \frac{\partial [\widehat{\alpha T}(x_2, \xi')]}{\partial \xi'} x_2 dx_2 dt'}_{F_4(t)} + 2h \mathcal{N}^{\mathbf{P}}(t) = \frac{M_3(t)}{b} \quad (11)$$

It is readily seen from Eq. (11) that the thermally induced bending moments can be reduced or even eliminated by applying sufficient voltage to the piezo devices to satisfy the conditions

$$\mathcal{N}^{\mathbf{P}}(t) = \frac{F_4(t)}{2bh} \quad (12)$$

resulting in

$$k(t) = 0 \quad \text{and} \quad N_T(t) = b F_2(t) \quad (13)$$

where N_T represents tractions in the x_1 -direction necessary to maintain plane sections which must be applied at the ends of the beam at $x_1 = 0$ and L . The latter produce creep strains $\epsilon_{11}^{\mathbf{C}}$ in addition to bending strains ϵ_{11} , if any, and are given by

$$\epsilon_{11}^{\mathbf{C}}(x_2, t) = \frac{1}{b} \int_{-\infty}^t \widehat{\psi}(x_2, \xi - \xi') \frac{\partial \widehat{N}_T(\xi')}{\partial \xi'} d\xi' \quad -h \leq x_2 \leq h \quad (14)$$

It is important to remember that the nature of the temperature and thermal expansions plays a central role in the generation of thermally induced bending as seen from Eqs. (5), (10) and (11). Nonhomogeneous material properties result from temperature distributions and, therefore, both must be included in the discussions. Since the beam is prismatic and the temperature distribution is limited to $T(x_2, t)$ in order to isolate and focus on thermal stains, a case of pure bending results, i. e. $M = M(t)$ only, and no shear stresses are generated due to bending actions as seen from Eq. (3). Table 1 summarizes these actions and their influence on beam bending.

Computational solution protocols

The solution involves the evaluation of the real (t) or pseudo (ξ) time integrals of Eqs. (1), (2), (5), (10), (11) and (14). This can be accomplished in any one of the following ways

1. In special cases Laplace or Fourier transforms can be used [24] and [25].

TABLE 1

TEMPERATURE FUNCTION $T(x_2, t)$	RELAXATION MODULUS $E[T(x_2, t)]$	BENDING	WEB SHEAR
even	even	no	no
even	odd	yes	no
odd	even	yes	no
odd	odd	yes	no

2. In more complicated problems without simple bending, a combination of spatial finite element and temporal finite difference or recurrence relation formulations are available [26] and [27].

Alternately for problems amenable to analytic solutions, Galerkin's method [28] can be used or the integral constitutive relations can be cast into differential forms of the form

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{P} \{ \sigma_{11}(x, t) \} &= SW(x_2) \mathbf{Q} \{ \epsilon_{11}(x, t) \} - SW^{\mathbf{T}}(x_2) \mathbf{Q}^{\mathbf{T}} \{ \alpha T(x, t) \} \\ &\quad - SW^{\mathbf{B}}(x_2) \mathbf{Q}^{\mathbf{B}} \{ \epsilon_{11}(x, t) \} - SW^{\mathbf{P}}(x_2) \mathbf{Q}^{\mathbf{P}} \{ \mathcal{E}_1(x, t) \} \end{aligned} \quad (15)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{P}^{\mathbf{D}} \{ D_1(x, t) \} &= SW^{\mathbf{D}}(x_2) \mathbf{Q}^{\mathbf{D}} \{ \epsilon_{11}(x, t) \} - SW^{\mathbf{DT}}(x_2) \mathbf{Q}^{\mathbf{DT}} \{ \alpha T(x, t) \} \\ &\quad + SW^{\mathbf{DP}}(x_2) \mathbf{Q}^{\mathbf{DP}} \{ \mathcal{E}_1(x, t) \} \end{aligned} \quad (16)$$

where the differential operators are

$$\mathbf{P}^{\mathbf{A}} = \sum_{n=0}^{R^{\mathbf{A}}} a_n^{\mathbf{A}}(x) \frac{\partial^n}{\partial t^n} \quad \mathbf{Q}^{\mathbf{A}} = \sum_{n=0}^{R^{\mathbf{A}}} b_n^{\mathbf{A}}(x) \frac{\partial^n}{\partial t^n} \quad (17)$$

with \mathbf{A} equal to the individual superscripts of Eqs. (15) and (16).

This system of equations can be solved by a Runge-Kutta approach, which leads to the simultaneous solution of Eqs. (15) and (16) with $R^* = R + R^{\mathbf{D}}$ or $R + R^{\mathbf{P}}$ representing the highest order derivatives for ϵ_{11} and D_1 or \mathcal{E}_1

$$\left. \begin{aligned} y_1 &= w_{11} & y_{R+4} &= D_{11} \text{ or } \mathcal{E}_1 \\ y_2 &= \dot{y}_1 & y_{R+5} &= \dot{y}_{R+4} \\ y_3 &= \dot{y}_2 & y_{R+6} &= \dot{y}_{R+5} \\ &\vdots & & \\ y_{R+3} &= \dot{y}_{R^*+2} & y_{R^*+4} &= \dot{y}_{R^*+3} \end{aligned} \right\} \quad (18)$$

While the above relations only show electrical field intensity vectors, strains are directly translatable into voltages \mathbf{V} , or vice versa, through the voltage–deformation (strain) linear constitutive relations

$$\mathbf{V}_k(x, t) = \frac{1}{A} \int_0^t \psi_{kk}^{\mathbf{P}}(x, t, t') \frac{\partial}{\partial t'} \left\{ \int_0^{t'} [A \phi_{kk}(x, t, s) + A^{\mathbf{P}} \phi_{kk}^{\mathbf{P}}(x, t, s)] \frac{\partial \epsilon_{kk}(x, s)}{\partial s} ds \right\} dt' \quad (19)$$

where $\psi^{\mathbf{P}}$ and $\phi^{\mathbf{P}}$ respectively are the piezoelectric creep and relaxation functions. The A s are the cross sectional areas of the beam and piezo devices. The isotropic constitutive relations, Eqs. (19), show that piezo-electro-viscoelasticity may require as many as eight distinct relaxation functions for material characterization (structure, bond, piezo device, voltage-deformation).

The inherent difficulty with the differential constitutive relations is that characterization of real materials requires values of $R^{\mathbf{A}}$ between 20 and 30. The linear integral constitutive relations, on the other hand, have relaxation functions represented by Prony series [29] of the type

$$\widehat{\phi}^{\mathbf{A}} [x, \xi^{\mathbf{A}}(x, t)] = \sum_{n=0}^{N^{\mathbf{A}}} \widehat{\phi}_n^{\mathbf{A}}(x) \exp \left[- \frac{\xi^{\mathbf{A}}(x, t)}{\widehat{\tau}_n^{\mathbf{A}}(x)} \right] \quad (20)$$

and the character of the integral relations does not change as $N^{\mathbf{A}}$ increases or decreases in value.

DISCUSSION OF RESULTS

As illustrative examples consider prismatic viscoelastic anisotropic beams with temperature distributions $T(x_2, t)$, such that the upper surface is at higher temperatures than the lower one. The beams are represented as composites with longitudinal and transverse fibers. Anisotropic viscoelastic properties are taken as fully temperature and time dependent. The piezoelectric devices and their bonding agents are considered viscoelastic as well. Distinct relaxation curves are assigned to the composite, bonding material and piezoelectric devices, thus rendering the ensemble nonhomogeneous and anisotropic (Figs. 2 and 3).

Bending and shear stresses, thermal expansions and piezoelectric sensing and control voltages are evaluated. Typical results are presented in Fig. 4 where the maximum time dependent deflections of a beam subjected to thermal loads are presented. Note the control effects of time dependent viscoelastic piezoelectric devices in decreasing beam deflections. While it is theoretically possible to eliminate deflections entirely (flat lower curve), such conditions require an excessive number of devices or large impractical voltages. The achievement of controlled deflections requires applications of prescribed piezo voltages through computer chip control.

Present day manufacturing methods of many structural materials other than metals, such as resin fiber-matrix composites, is sufficiently imprecise so as to produce scattered material properties. Consequently, material property coefficients in constitutive and failure relations need to be represented by stochastic distributions. While viscoelastic analytical tools for probabilistic stress-strain and failure analyses are available in [30] and [31] very little statistical experimental relaxation and failure data have appeared in the literature.

Viscoelastic failure criteria, such as ultimate stresses, degrade in time independently of relaxation moduli. Some failure mechanisms observed in composites are substantially different from those observed in metals [20]. For example, delamination is a phenomenon unique to composites.

From a design analysis point of view, one needs only to consider delamination onset because at that stage a structure has for all practical purposes failed, particularly if it is a light weight flight structure. An expression for the temperature, moisture and time dependency of uniaxial composite failure stresses was formulated in [31] where an extensive review of available experimental composite failure data has been presented as well. Using such data, they have formulated deterministic and stochastic delamination failure analyses. Experimental results (Fig. 5) indicate that uniaxial deterministic delamination onset stresses in tension and shear obey relatively simple laws.

In [21] deterministic and stochastic invariant combined load failure criteria have been developed in terms of two relations involving uniaxial applied and failure stresses. Additional details can be found in [31]. Limited experimental results in the literature indicate that the uniaxial failure distributions for composites are of the Weibull type.

The time t_{LF} corresponding to the largest value of $\tilde{P}_F(x, t_{LF})$ at a point $x_i = c_i$ in a structure is the life time or survival time (Fig. 6). In stochastic probabilistic structural failure analysis, one seeks similar points or regions where $\tilde{P}_F(x, t_{LF}) = 1$ or alternately the maximum probability value $\tilde{P}_F(x, t_{LF}) < 1$ to indicate survival probabilities. A similar class of problems arises from the imposition of design survival times t_{LFD} with each specification corresponding to a design failure probability $\tilde{P}_{FD}(t_{LFD}) \leq 1$, or conversely the prescription of a $\tilde{P}_{FD}(t_{LFD})$ with a resulting t_{LFD} .

Further passive control can also be achieved by tailored viscoelastic materials designed to perform in an *a priori* prescribed manner to satisfy desired service performance as formulated in [32] and [33].

Additional research investigations currently in progress are examining control of column and lateral buckling due to thermal stresses, Timoshenko beams, effects of nonlinear materials and large deformations under thermal stresses, and damping effects of viscoelastic sandwich structures.

CONCLUSIONS

Light weight piezoelectric viscoelastic devices can be effectively used to actively or passively control composite viscoelastic beams subject to thermal as well as conventional loadings. This can be accomplished by utilizing the native viscoelastic dissipative properties of the structure and of the piezoelectric devices and by providing suitable input voltages to viscoelastic piezoelectric devices, by prescribed electric displacements or by controlling the output emf through appropriate resistors. Additionally, the same piezoelectric devices can also be used for deformation sensing.

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Fig. 1 - LONGITUDINAL VIEW OF BEAM

Fig. 2 - Anisotropic Relaxation Moduli

Fig. 3 - Beam, Piezo and Bond Relaxation Moduli

Fig. 4 - Maximum Beam Deflection

Fig. 5 - Uniaxial Delamination Stresses [20]

Fig. 6 - Probability of Failure